

OCEAN ICE News – May 2026

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to May's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as an OCEAN ICE Publication, and OCEAN ICE featured in European Correspondent and highlighting April's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in June. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in June!

Meet the Team: Andrew Meijers

Check out our latest 'Meet the Team' feature on Andrew Meijers, one of the science coordinators for OCEAN ICE, working at British Antarctic Survey

Read the feature on Andrew [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Publication: Atmospheric rivers and winter sea ice drive recent reversal in Antarctic ice mass loss

Ruth Mottram from WP3 in OCEAN ICE contributed to a paper published in nature on 'Atmospheric rivers and winter sea ice drive recent reversal in Antarctic ice mass loss'.

Since about 2000, Antarctica has been steadily losing ice, adding to global sea-level rise. However, satellite data show that since around 2020 this trend has temporarily reversed, with Antarctica gaining ice overall.

Read the abstract [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Feature in European Correspondent on the A23a Iceberg

OCEAN ICE was featured in the European Correspondent on April 23, discussing the life and death of the A23a iceberg and the wider context of the Southern Ocean/Antarctica for global climate and sea level. The interview with Andrew Meijers focused on the path and steady melt of the A23a megaberg as it travelled towards its eventual disintegration in the Polar Front but used this as a vehicle to discuss OCEAN ICE science and the Southern Ocean. The interview touched on the deep uncertainty in future sea level rise projections, as well as the 'Greenlandification' of the Southern Ocean - both topics that OCEAN ICE has advanced significantly over the last four years.

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The English version of the article can be found here: <https://europeancorrespondent.com/en/r/the-worlds-biggest-iceberg-is-almost-gone>

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – April

Climate Coffee with Jens Terhaar on Record Sea Surface Temperature Jump in 2023–2024

Over the past months, global sea surface temperatures (SSTs) have quietly done something quite important: they have returned to levels below those before the pronounced jump observed in 2023/24 (<https://climatereanalyzer.org/clim/ss...>). Earlier this year, we published a study in Nature magazine (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s4158...>) showing that abrupt SST jumps of this magnitude can arise solely from internal climate variability, as climate models can simulate such events without invoking an external shock or a permanent system shift. A key feature of these simulated jumps is that they are transient - temperatures typically relax back to pre-jump levels about two years later. What is striking is that the real-world evolution has closely followed this pattern. Observed SSTs have now also returned to pre-jump levels, roughly two months later than the model range suggested. Given the small number of simulations with such high jumps (8 models), the range for the return remains uncertain, and a 2-month delay is well within uncertainty. The return of SSTs below pre-jump levels thus adds confidence to the interpretation that the 2023/24 jump may have been driven by internal variability rather than a fundamental reorganisation of the climate system. However, until we have observations over the next few years, we still cannot exclude a fundamental system shift. At the same time, the relatively late recovery may point toward a climate system that responds more strongly to forcing than many models currently suggest - in other words, a potentially higher equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS) and stronger underlying warming. This interpretation aligns with another recent study of ours by Linus Vogt (<https://esd.copernicus.org/articles/1...>), which shows that many climate models simulate too little Antarctic sea ice compared to observations. Because Antarctic sea ice strongly affects how much heat the Southern Ocean absorbs, this bias can lead to an underestimation of ECS.

Taken together, these results highlight an important nuance: short-term climate variability can produce large, temporary excursions, but the climate system's background sensitivity still matters enormously for long-term warming. Understanding both - and not confusing one for the other - is crucial for interpreting recent extremes and for improving future projections. At the same time, recent events are a reminder of how little we still understand about the climate system, and how important it is to keep questioning, testing, and refining our models as new observations emerge.

Publication: Terhaar, J., Burger, F.A., Vogt, L. et al. Record sea surface temperature jump in 2023–2024 unlikely but not unexpected. *Nature* 639, 942–946 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-08...>

Climate Coffee

23 April 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Jens Terhaar
(University Bern)

**Record sea surface temperature jump
in 2023–2024 unlikely but not
unexpected**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch, the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in June, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Torsten Albrecht on Mapping tipping risks from Antarctic ice basins under global warming

18 June 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

Thu 18 June 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST

Online

Torsten Albrecht

(Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research)

Mapping tipping risks from Antarctic ice basins under global warming

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 23rd – 27th June 2026, [IGS Meeting](#), Dartmouth, US
- 8th -19th August 2026, [SCAR Open Science Conference & Meetings](#), Norway, Oslo
- 17th - 19th August 2026, [FRISP Meeting 2026](#), Sweden, Kristineberg

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

OCEAN:ICE

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